

Environmental Influences on Adsorption of 1, 3 Dichloropropene by 'AKLI' Bentonite

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Investigations on the effect of time, pH, exchangeable cations, organic matter and temperature on the adsorption of telone on bentonite showed that a minimum period of 8 hours for hydrogen saturated and 10 hours for sodium saturated bentonite was required for completion of the process of adsorption. The adsorption of telone increased with a decrease in pH. The interaction was cation dependent and occurred mostly due to ion exchange. Organic matter in form of humic acid increased the degree of adsorption due to interaction of the telone molecule with organic matter. The process was temperature sensitive and decreased with a rise in temperature.

TELONE (1, 3-dichloropropene) is widely employed as a soil fumigant to combat the destructive action of plant parasitic nematodes and other soil organisms. In contact with soil colloid it is readily adsorbed. In recent communications the authors¹⁻³ proposed reaction mechanisms for its adsorption on acid and base saturated clays. Work by other investigators revealed that among several factors adsorption of pesticides on soil colloids is affected by pH, organic matter, type of cation on the clay surface, temperature and molecular structure⁴⁻⁸. Since the phenomenon of adsorption influences the fate and behaviour of a pesticide in the soil system, and makes it possible to calculate proper pesticide doses and since adsorption itself is affected by environmental conditions, the aim of the present study was to investigate the influence of certain critical factors such as time, pH, exchangeable cations, organic matter and temperature on telone sorption by 'Akli' bentonite.

Experimental

The bentonite used in these studies was obtained from 'Akli' in Rajasthan. X-ray diffraction showed that it was mainly composed of montmorillonite. After removal of organic matter with hydrogen peroxide, the clay was dispersed and less than 2u fraction converted into chloride free sodium and hydrogen saturated forms by Aldrich and Buchanan's method¹⁰. The concentration of the suspensions was 11.0 g per litre. The cation exchange capacity of the bentonite was found to be 90 meq per 100 g.

For the investigation of the effect of time on telone adsorption, the experiments were conducted at the pH values of 6.9 in case of sodium saturated bentonite and 3.5 in case of hydrogen saturated bentonite in which eight samples of 10 ml of hydrogen and sodium saturated bentonite suspensions were treated with a constant amount of an alcoholic solution (2.5 ml of telone solution containing 10 g per litre) of telone. The mixtures were adjusted to a

constant volume of 25 ml with alcohol and distilled water. The tubes were shaken at $28 \pm 0.1^\circ$ in a thermostatic water bath. Samples were drawn at intervals of 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 16 and 20 hours respectively and centrifuged. The amount of telone remaining unadsorbed was then immediately estimated in the supernatant liquids using silver thiocyanate ferric alum method¹¹. The results for the effect of time on the amount of telone adsorbed by hydrogen and sodium saturated bentonite are represented (Fig. 1).

For the investigation of the effect of pH on telone sorption, sodium saturated bentonite suspensions were treated with 0.1N HNO₃ and 0.1N NaOH respectively, to obtain the desired equilibrium levels of pH (2.0, 3.5, 5.0, 7.0, 8.5 and 10.0). The adsorption of telone was then studied at each of the above pH values as described below in case of exchangeable cations. The results are given in Fig. 1.

The adsorption of telone on hydrogen and sodium saturated bentonites was determined by taking 10 ml aliquots containing 110 mg of the appropriate clay in a large number of glass stoppered tubes and adding different amounts of an alcoholic solution (10 g per litre) of telone. The mixtures were diluted to 25 ml with alcohol and distilled water so that the alcohol content of the mixtures was minimum and the same in all cases. After intermittent shaking and standing for 12 hours at a temperature $28 \pm 0.1^\circ$, their pH and conductance were recorded. The suspensions were then centrifuged. The supernatants showed the formation of chloride and residual telone in them. The chloride ions and the residual telone were estimated in the supernatants with and without refluxing the supernatants with N alcoholic KOH, using silver thiocyanate ferric alum method¹¹. The difference gave the amount of telone remaining in the equilibrium liquid after adsorption. The amount of telone adsorbed was calculated from the amount of telone added and

Fig. 1. Effect of Time and pH on Adsorption of Telone by Sodium and Hydrogen Saturated Bentonites

- Sodium saturated bentonite
- Hydrogen saturated bentonite
- Sodium saturated bentonite

remaining after contact with clay. The results of adsorption and the pH and conductivity changes produced are represented in Figs. 3 to 4 respectively. For a study of temperature effect this experiment was also done at $42 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

The effect of organic matter on the adsorption of the nematocide was then examined by taking 10 ml aliquots of hydrogen and sodium saturated clay suspensions in glass stoppered tubes and adding 50 mg of humic acid in each case in the first set of experiments and 100 mg of humic acid in the second set and then adding varying amounts of 1% solution of telone to the suspensions as described earlier. The pH and conductometric variations produced during interaction of telone with hydrogen and sodium saturated bentonites in presence of humic acid were also recorded. The results of adsorption, pH and conductivity variations are reported (vide Figs. 3 to 4). The adsorption of telone on humic acid alone was also studied.

Results and Discussion

The effect of time on adsorption of telone is presented in Fig. 1. Adsorption slowly increased with time till the systems approached equilibrium at 8 hours in case of hydrogen saturated bentonite and 10 hours in case of sodium saturated bentonite. The

slow adsorption of telone by bentonites appeared to be due to certain interactions which must be taking place between the pesticide and the lateral, planar and interior surfaces of the clay. A period 8 and 10 hours for hydrogen and sodium bentonites, respectively, appeared to be sufficient for attainment of equilibrium and for carrying out further adsorption experiments.

The effect of pH on the extent of adsorption of telone on bentonite is also illustrated in Fig. 1. In the range studied the adsorption continuously increased with a decrease in pH till it became almost constant below pH 3.5. The results were in agreement with the findings of many other workers who explained the increase in adsorption of pesticides with decreasing pH as being due to protonation of the molecule followed by adsorption. The reaction mechanism in our case was as follows :

At higher pH values this interaction did not occur to any appreciable extent. Whatever adsorption

occurred at higher pH values was due to van der Waals forces and was low⁷. These findings indicated that under natural conditions the rate of telone needed for nematocidal action in montmorillonite soils would vary with soil pH. Acidic soils with a lower pH will require larger doses of the chemical to overcome the increased rate of adsorption. This was in agreement with the results reported by Burnside and Behrens^{1,2} on the phytotoxicity of simazine as affected by soil pH.

The results of adsorption of telone on hydrogen and sodium saturated bentonites are illustrated in Fig.2. The shapes of the isotherms^{1,3} and the

nature of pH and conductivity variations produced (Figs 2 to 4) during the interaction suggested a definite cation exchange reaction mechanism between telone and hydrogen and sodium saturated bentonites followed by penetration of the pesticide in the micropores as already discussed in an earlier publication of the authors². To examine the effect of organic matter on the adsorption, the adsorption experiments were, however, redone to obtain similarity of conditions of experiments. The isotherms did not follow the Langmuir relation $C/x/m = \frac{1}{KB} + \frac{C}{B}$. From the shapes of adsorption isotherms (Fig.2, curves 1 and 2) it was clear that a

FIG 2 EFFECT OF EXCHANGEABLE CATIONS AND ORGANIC MATTER ON THE ADSORPTION OF TELONE BY SODIUM AND HYDROGEN SATURATED BENTONITES

- Sodium saturated bentonite
- 0.5% Humic acid + sodium saturated bentonite
- ▲ 1.0% Humic acid + sodium saturated bentonite
- Hydrogen saturated bentonite
- △ 0.5% Humic acid + hydrogen saturated bentonite
- 1.0% Humic acid + hydrogen saturated bentonite

larger amount of telone was adsorbed on sodium saturated bentonite in the earlier stages as compared to hydrogen saturated bentonite. The nature of exchangeable cation on the bentonite surface was thus very important in determining the degree of adsorption of telone and the optimum dose for nematocidal action in soils. This deduction was in agreement with the findings of other workers^{14,15} on the adsorption of organic pesticides on clays and soils.

The values obtained for the adsorption of telone on hydrogen and sodium saturated bentonites in presence of 0.5 and 1.0 per cent humic acid are given in Fig.2. An examination of the curves (Fig.2, curves 3 to 6) showed that bentonites acquired a higher capacity for adsorption in the presence of humic acid and it increased with an increase in the percentage of organic matter (Fig.2, curves 3 to 6). This suggested the possibility of an interaction between the organic matter present in bentonites and the nematocide. The humic acid is bound to interact with clays forming some kind of clay-organo-complexes. Hance⁷ suggested that, in soil,

clay and organic matter associate in such a manner that little of the clay mineral surface was available to pesticide molecules. On the other hand, Mortland¹⁶ concluded from an investigation on a model system, that organic compounds in soil organic matter upon interaction with clay may facilitate and stabilise adsorption of pesticides beyond that observed in a purely inorganic clay system. Our data appeared to be in agreement with Mortland's suggestion. Thus humic acid on interaction with bentonites and present as a clay organo-complex may facilitate the adsorption of telone on the clays in soils.

In support of the above conclusion the results of adsorption of telone on humic acid alone were studied. The results of pH and conductivity variations during adsorption of nematocide on humic acid indicated an interaction between telone and humic acid. Humic acids possessed functional groups such as phenolic hydroxyl, alcoholic hydroxyl and carboxyl groups which on dissociation could participate in exchange reactions⁸. The interaction between telone and the organic matter

Fig. 3. Variation in pH with amount of telone adsorbed by Sodium and Hydrogen Saturated Bentonites and in presence of Organic matter.

- Sodium saturated bentonite
- 0.5% Humic acid + sodium saturated bentonite
- ▲ 1.0% Humic acid + sodium saturated bentonite
- Hydrogen saturated bentonite
- △ 0.5% Humic acid + hydrogen saturated bentonite
- 1.0% Humic acid + hydrogen saturated bentonite

Fig. 4. Variation in Electrical Conductivity with amount of Telone adsorbed by Sodium and Hydrogen Saturated Bentonites and in presence of Organic matter.

- Sodium saturated bentonite
- 0.5% Humic acid + sodium saturated bentonite
- ▲ 1.0% Humic acid + sodium saturated bentonite
- Hydrogen saturated bentonite
- △ 0.5% Humic acid + hydrogen saturated bentonite
- 1.0% Humic acid + hydrogen saturated bentonite

thus occurred by the following mechanism,

where R was the carboxyl, phenolic, alcoholic or hydroquinone group present in humic acid. This process increased the adsorption of the nematocide on hydrogen and sodium saturated bentonites in presence of humic acid.

The decrease in pH and a rise in electrical conductivity (Figs.3 and 4) characteristically in the same manner as in the case of humic acid was as a result of the formation of HCl during the interaction of telone both with the organic matter, as indicated above, and with the Na- and H-bentonites as described earlier. The additive effect was responsible for an increased adsorption of telone on the clay-organo complexes. The results found support from the work of Khan¹⁷ on the interaction of bipyridylum herbicides with organo-clay complex.

The effect of temperature on the adsorption of telone by sodium and hydrogen saturated bentonites at a pH value of 6.9 in case of sodium saturated bentonite and 3.6 in case of hydrogen saturated bentonite indicated a 'substantial effect of temperature on adsorption of telone on the sodium and hydrogen saturated bentonites. Over the entire range studied an increase in temperature resulted in a decrease in adsorption. This was in agreement with the general phenomenon observed in adsorption of pesticides on clays^{18,19}. Adsorptive processes are exothermic and therefore an increase in temperature was followed by a decrease in adsorption as observed in our case. Soils in tropical regions will, therefore, need lower doses of the chemical for nematocidal action subject to control over other environmental factors as compared to soils in cold regions.

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